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**LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK MEDIA
DISCOURSE: STRUCTURE, FEATURES AND DISCURSIVE
PRACTICE**

Annotation: This article gives information about one of the institutional types of discourse - media discourse, which appears to be a multifaceted complex phenomenon that is in constant development under the influence of various extralinguistic factors and reflects changes in society at the linguistic level.

Key words: linguistic analysis, media discourse, structure, features and discursive practice.

The word, which carried a new, previously unknown meaning, always excited the consciousness of a person, causing an increased interest in those objects that were designated with this word. The process of transition from word to statement, text marked the beginning of the emergence of mass communication, which is already at the present stage realized in such a type of discourse as media discourse or mass media discourse.

Therefore, since ancient times, scientists have been trying to identify patterns in the functioning of the word in various structural associations (phrase, phrase, sentence, text, etc.) and thematic contexts, compare the results obtained on the material of different languages, and establish common and distinctive features of the studied phenomena. Attempts are regularly made to systematize the data obtained. However, the technological progress that accompanies the development of society directly affects the changes that take place in the language and, accordingly, in the general picture of the world.

Many works have been devoted to the study of mass media, so let's turn to the analysis of the main ones in order to get the most complete picture of the existing approaches to the consideration of media discourse.

The classical approach to the study of mass media was developed by G. Lascyell, according to which the study of mass communication was carried out based on the participants, content, channel and result of communication. That is, the solution of any research problems is carried out without taking into account the linguistic features of the communicator and the factors of its communication. It also does not take into account the communicative situation and much more.

Thus, we see that the role of the communicator as a communicator directing communication in accordance with his plans and goals with this approach is exaggerated, which is not true, since the sender takes an active part in the

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communicative process, information exchange is impossible without him. His plans and goals are not decisive in media communication, since there are other factors that do not depend on the intentions of the communicator [1].

According to the cognitive approach, the mass media are not only a mirror of the events taking place around us, but also, thanks to their interpretation through media channels, a media picture of the world is created. The most important concepts at the cognitive level of studying media texts are the information society, the linguistic picture of the world, ideology and culture [2].

In the framework of the evocative approach, on the contrary, the difference between the roles of the addresser and the addressee is taken into account, which allows avoiding the displacement of the addresser beyond the framework of communication and taking into account the influence of both parties on the course of the communication process: initiating communication on a specific topic, maintaining it in one format or another and implementing it. communication purposes. At the same time, the intention of the addresser does not apply to the entire process [3].

Thus, we see that the approach proposed by G. Lascyell is not entirely acceptable, since evocative processes in media discourse require consideration from the standpoint of cognitive linguistics, communication science, discursive linguistics and other scientific fields, which will allow us to fully describe the phenomenon under study, since media discourse is not a set of loosely interconnected elements, but a whole system, a single whole, i.e. a full-fledged discourse with coherence, indicating the completeness of the discourse in question and its ability to function independently in the information space.

When considering such a phenomenon as media discourse, we first of all turn to the consideration of the concept of "discourse" as a whole. Following B. M. Gasparov, we agree that "discourse is the central moment of human "life in language"". It seems indisputable to us that discourse can be compared with linguistic existence, a particle of a continuously moving stream of human experience [4].

Discourse, having a form of representation and consolidation of a linguistic sign, depending on a number of conditions [5], on the one hand, and being at the same time an utterance in conjunction with cognitive frames that determine the content and form of the utterance [6], on the other hand, is "naturally occurring coherent speech or written documents" in which the use of language in a social context is determined in a certain way, manifested through interaction or dialogue between interlocutors [7].

A thorough definition of the term "discourse" from a linguistic point of view was, in our opinion, given by D. Shiffrin, who interprets the concept from three sides. Within the framework of the first approach, from the standpoint of formally or structurally oriented linguistics, discourse is interpreted as "a language above the level of a sentence or phrase".

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The second, functional, approach defines discourse as any "use of language in a broad socio-cultural context". According to the third version of the interpretation of discourse, its definition emphasizes the interaction of form and function, i.e. discourse is not a primitive set of isolated units of the linguistic structure "more than a sentence", but an integral set of functionally organized, contextualized units of language use [8].

However, the interpretation of discourse as a text taken in the event aspect in combination with various factors, including pragmatic ones, which reflects the process of turning a text into a speech event and allows us to consider discourse as a speech "immersed in life", is distinguished by the greatest capacity. Having studied various definitions of the concept of "discourse", we come to the conclusion that they can be combined within the framework of such approaches as communicative (discourse is interpreted as "verbal communication (speech, use, functioning of language)").

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